

Microdetermination of tungsten in environmental samples by differential pulse polarography

P. Sharma* and Taruna Rathore

Electroanalytical Laboratory, Department of Chemistry, J. N. V. University, Jodhpur-342 005, India

Fax : 91-0291-511191

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The optimum analytical conditions are found for trace determination of tungsten in various matrices using differential pulse polarography. The limit of determination of 0.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ is achieved with a precision of ± 0.39 standard deviation.

Electrochemical methods have good potential for speciation and quantitation studies of a number of metal ions in different matrices¹. Trace level determination of tungsten at a graphite electrode using anodic stripping voltammetry was reported by Malakhova *et al.*². Applications of differential pulse mode with mercury drop electrode for the determination of tungsten in aqueous solutions has also been described³. The catalytic current polarographic determination of tungsten was shown by Kurbatov *et al.*⁴.

In the present work, a differential pulse polarographic (DPP) method has been proposed for the determination of tungsten using sodium tartrate in acidic medium. The method was used to determine tungsten contents in samples of natural water, coalmine water, industrial effluent and soil.

Results and Discussion

Polarographic characteristics of tungsten :

Different supporting electrolytes, viz. ammonium acetate, ammonium tartrate, ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer, borate buffer, potassium nitrate and sodium tartrate were studied to observe electroreduction of tungsten at a dropping mercury electrode. A combination of sodium tartrate (0.56 M) in hydrochloric acid (5.8 M) was found to be a suitable medium where two distinct waves were obtained for the stepwise reduction of tungsten(VI) as shown in Fig. 1(b). The limiting current of the first wave representing $\text{W}^{\text{VI}} - \text{W}^{\text{V}}$ was not found linear in the concentration range $(0.10-0.30) \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ for tungsten. Therefore, for quantitation first wave was not used. The second wave corresponding to $\text{W}^{\text{V}} - \text{W}^{\text{III}}$ was chosen for further studies of which wave height increased linearly with the concentration of tungsten in range $(0.10-0.45) \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$.

Optimal conditions for tungsten determination :

W^{VI} also showed sharp differential pulse peak (DP) at

Fig. 1. (a) DP polarogram of W^{VI} in presence of Pb^{II} in 0.56 M sodium tartrate in 5.8 M HCl, W^{VI} and Pb^{II} , 2.0 ppm each. modulation amplitude 50 mV, pulse duration, 57 ms, clock time of pulse, 1 s; scan rate, 5 mV/s (b) DC polarogram of W^{VI} in 0.56 M sodium tartrate in 5.8 M HCl, W^{VI} , $1 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$

-0.57 V. A linearity of peak height was observed in the 0.05-14.0 ppm range of W^{VI} concentration. The characteristics of the calibration curve were as follows : slope, $0.56 \pm$

1.08×10^{-2} ; coefficient of correlation (r), 0.998; standard deviation (sd), 0.16. The detection limit of 0.05 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ was achieved under the experimental conditions.

Interference :

DP polarograms of tungsten were also recorded in presence of other common cations, such as Fe^{III} , Zn^{II} , Ni^{II} , Mn^{II} and Pb^{II} . The standard reduction potential of ferric iron is positive (>0.40 V), thus iron does not interfere in the determination. Similarly, Zn, Ni and Mn do not show DP peaks prior to the diffusion of supporting electrolyte, i.e. -0.76 V vs Ag/AgCl. The DP peak of lead was noticed at -0.34 V which was distinguishable from tungsten at -0.57 V [Fig. 1(a)]. Thus, these metal ions did not interfere during the determination of tungsten by DPP.

Applications :

The DPP reduction of W^{VI} in 0.56 M sodium tartrate in hydrochloric acid medium was made the basis for tungsten determination in soils, coalmine water and industrial effluents. The prepared samples were taken into the polarographic cell and DP polarograms were recorded in the potential range of 0.0 to -0.8 V. The peak currents were measured at -0.57 V after making blank corrections.

Quantitation in all observations was made by standard addition method⁵. The results of tungsten determination are summarized in Table I.

Table I. DPP determination of tungsten

Sample	N	Tungsten concentration (ppm)		
		Min.	Max.	Average
Soil	4	1.415	2.622	1.839
Industrial waste water ^a	3	0.359	0.734	0.493
Tap water ^a	4	ND	ND	ND
Coalmine water	3	0.349	0.359	0.354

N = number of determinations. ND = Not detected.

^aMainly of steel factories. ^bUniversity campus.

Atomic absorption spectrophotometry⁶ was used to compare the results obtained by DPP. The tungsten concentration in soil samples by DPP and AAS were found within the limits of 1.415–2.622 (Av. 1.839) and 1.50–2.80 (Av. 1.875) ppm, respectively.

Conclusion :

DPP provides a simple approach for the rapid determination of tungsten in presence of other common metal ions without any interference. The comparison of results obtained by DPP suggests the validity of the proposed method.

Experimental

A polarographic analyzer (174-A) in conjunction with a drop timer (174/70) and X-Y recorder (RE 0074) from Princeton Applied Research Corporation, EG & G, USA

was used for DC and DPP experiments. The instrumental settings for DPP were as follows : a dropping mercury electrode was used as the working electrode, modulation amplitude 50 mV; pulse duration, 57 ms; clock time of pulse 1 s and scan rate 5 mV/s. Potentials were measured against an Ag/AgCl electrode. A platinum wire was used as an auxiliary electrode in all measurements.

An inductively coupled plasma based atomic emission spectrophotometer (model 1M Jobin-Yuan, France) was also used for sample analysis. The instrument has polychromator, sequentia facility and axial viewing plasma frequency 48.68 MHz. It consisted concentric quartz nebulizer and holographic blazed grating with 3600 grooves.

The samples of soil and industrial waste were collected from the selected site of Degana and Jodhpur city in Rajasthan, while coalmine water was collected from Brijrajnagar, Orissa. Samples were acidified with hydrochloric acid (ultra pure) to adjust pH ~ 2 . The organic matters were destroyed by treating the samples (100 ml aliquot) with conc. nitric acid⁷.

Moisture-free, fine powdered soil was weighed and leached out overnight with nitric acid. Vigorous mixing and excessive washing was done and finally samples were concentrated by evaporation for analysis⁸.

Test solutions were deaerated by passing nitrogen for 20 min, which was purified by bubbling it through a vanadous chloride-scrubbing solution. Chemicals used were of A.R. grade. All the experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 1^\circ$.

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